

EXISTENCE OF COLLABORATIVE WORK BETWEEN COLLEAGUES AND PUPILS, ITS IMPORTANCE TO SUCCEED IN MANAGING SCHOOL DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

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ABSTRACT

This paper sheds some light on the importance of collaborative work in school management success and formation of team work to improve good relations between school leaders, colleagues and learner individuals. And also shows that effective teaching experiences can be more useful when old methods are shared and evaluated with new modern ideas.

Key words: *Teamwork, innovative practices, professional development, close interaction.*

I. Introduction

Collaboration between teachers contributes to school improvement and student success. Collaboration between teachers is a powerful professional development activity that can help teachers to improve their subject knowledge, think about teaching strategies in different ways, share experience and learn new ideas from each other to try in the classroom. For first and most beneficial side of collaboration is that teachers have an opportunity of developing teaching skills by using different methods those used by their colleagues and showed effective results. Teachers who work collaboratively tend to use new innovative practices and succeed in managing the classroom faster rather than the teacher who prefers not to be involved in teamwork.

Collaboration leads aimed success when it also include close interaction with pupils other than teachers themselves. There can be some learners who need the support of the peers as well as teacher motivation. The result of nice collaboration between them can be seen in the rise of pupils' self-esteem and interest towards the course.

II.Literature review.

According to the research, teachers' professional skills in their own sphere are effected by external facilitators, such as necessary amount of resources , relationship among colleagues and critical reflection (Ciampa & Gallagher, 2016; Furtak & Heredia, 2014; Schipper et al., 2017; Wardrip, Gomez & Gomez, 2015). Teacher's successful collaboration is based on the working process that leads colleagues' aimed result of task (Vangrieken et al. (2015), Examples of process factors that catalyze teacher collaboration mentioned in previous research include goal clarity (Alles, Seidel & Gröschner, 2018), experimentation and conflict processes that provide engagement in effective learning activities deals with one's beliefs (Achinstein, 2002; Owen, 2016; Schipper, Goei, de Vries & van Veen, 2017; Tam, 2015a)

Methodology

Research method: Interview.A type of data collecting tool that requires structured conversation between interviewer who provides questions and interviewee to give answers.

When: 20th of October; Where: at school; How: face to face; Data collecting tool: Interview.

Participants

Shermatova Muxlisa – work place: 16th school in Ferghana region; experience: 1 year; teaches 7th grade pupils; level: B2;

Olimjonova To'lganoy – work place: 51th school in Ferghana region; experience: 2 year; teaches 1st, 2nd grade pupils; level: B2;

Ahmedova Zarnigor – work place: 9th school in Ferghana region; experience: 2 year; teaches 1st,2nd grade pupils; level: C1 ;

O'ktamova Asila – work place: 29th school in Ferghana region;

experience: 2 year; teaches 1st,2nd,8th,9th grade pupils; level: C1;

Sodiqova Mohlarbegim – work place: 15th in Ferghana region; experience: 1year; teaches 6th grade pupils; level: B2.

Interview questions:

- 1.If your students do not want to be involved in the activity what action will you take?
- 2.Do you ask your colleagues' help from time to time? If yes in what kind of situations?
- 3.Can you manage bad- mannered students yourself? What methods do you use to get on well with them in the classroom?

III.Data analysis and discussion

5 students who both study at the Ferghana State university and have about 1 and 2 year work experience at school were included in the interview. While some of the responses given by interviewees were the same, some of them tried to make additional viewpoint. In the first situation, 60% of the solution was implementing prizes and bonuses to make all of the students active during the lesson. Only one participant claimed to be strict, while changing the activity or the method with another was supported by one other interviewee. For the next two questions those were about asking colleagues help in terms of classroom management, all interviewees mentioned that they all feel necessary for colleagues help and advice.

As far as, bad-mannered pupils in the classroom, showing strictness is only solution for 4 participants, with the exception of M. who uses the method of giving disruptive students important responsibilities among other pupils.

Surely, I satisfied all the given responses and I consider professional teacher should learn to rule the class by balancing strictness and supportive interaction as well as provide pupils with enough high motivation.

Conclusion

As considering the essence of collaborative work in terms of school improvement, close relations are required to be established among school individuals. Teachers will be able to handle classroom duties effectively when they are given the opportunity of using colleagues' help or advice at least. Exchanging learnt practices

and variety of theoretical solutions for classroom issues may help teachers to overcome daily school stress and in most cases teamwork can make great professionals from young teachers who are struggling in new job in the long term.

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